

ABOUT THE USE OF ACTIVITIES FOR DEVELOPING DISCOURSE COMPETENCE

Yoqubova Mohira Otaniyoz qizi¹

MA Department Student of
Navoi Pedagogical University

Nasirova U.K.²

Supervisor: PhD,

senior lecturer at the department of

¹English language and literature Faculty

²English Language Teaching

Methodology №2, UzSWLU

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6775098>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 28th May 2022

Accepted: 02nd June 2022

Online: 05th June 2022

KEY WORDS

B2, student, competence, activity.

ABSTRACT

This article discusses the activities for the development of discourse competence of B2 level students, its specificity, importance and direction.

The most important part of making an audience understand your material is knowing the material yourself. Through complex rhetoric, you could convince an audience that you are an expert when you are not, but this would be disingenuous and unethical.

Instead, be sure to have a true and thorough understanding of the subject matter. If you do not, be upfront on this point, and suggest that you could both benefit from further education.

When possible be the first part of our professor's example and know all that you can. But unlike the professor, you will use your knowledge of sociolinguistics to more effectively illuminate your point. It is one of the most important key factors to know how to improve communicative competence.

Whatever the subject, first keep in mind what it is like to be in the position of the learner, and to not be acquainted with the

topic. As our specific field of expertise becomes more ingrained into us, it becomes easier to forget what it was like to learn it for the first time.

Instead, consider the foundational knowledge that was necessary for you to get to the more advanced knowledge. Like the professor who has lost touch with his students, skipping the beginning or intermediate steps of learning can lose people in the fray. Instead, risk over-explaining. Without taking it to the extreme of boring people to the point of losing them, simply ensure that they know too much when it comes to foundational knowledge.

The next key factor in knowing how to improve communicative competence is to reduce social and speaking anxiety. A critical element of your content is how it is delivered. Ultimately, this is our entire struggle, as all of the information presented by the good professor and the boring

professor is virtually the same. One just knows how to deliver it in a way that their audience can understand and appreciate.

The first step in getting your delivery where it needs to be in making your performance without anxiety, or with as little anxiety as possible.

Following all of the points included in this list will go quite a distance towards anxiety reduction, but keep in mind anxiety is often part of a larger lifestyle issue as well. Lack of sleep, dehydration, and improper nutrition all play a role in setting you up for failure before you even step on stage, so to speak.

Meditation is a powerful tool that ties into anxiety reduction, which leads us to our next point.

Although a competently conversational speaker is not necessarily planning out their every move, they will usually go in with at least a rough guideline or game plan for their attack on the information.

The best way to do is actually not by taking the hyper-analytical approach of making step-by-step plans for every action.

Instead, take a moment to close your eyes and visualize how the presentation would go under ideal circumstances. Be thorough here: imagine everything from your posture, tone of voice, and content, all the way to your audience's reactions.

Too much planning can lead to cognitive dissonance when things start to stray from the plan, but visualization simply primes you. By taking a moment to imagine the perfect outcome, you subconsciously assure yourself that it is indeed possible and that you can achieve it.

There are a lot of other adjustments that the teacher can make with regards to the content of the text, such as readjusting in random order the text's paragraphs and

asking them to find the correct order in which the text is put together. This serves as a way to actively introduce the information pertaining to the lead character of the story, a woman back in 1884, Sarah, who inherits the wealth of the Winchester family, after the deaths of her husband and child, and reinstates the family to California, with plans to build a huge house, as a way to start over and maintain the family balance.

This initial task aids the students to get better acquainted with the text, and also assists them to explore the function of certain vocabulary items, in order to understand the text to its full extent.

As far the activation of the vocabulary items is concerned, we can start by asking them some questions about expressions used in the second paragraph of the text, to establish the level of their understanding of the key terminology: "inherited", "fell into a deep depression", "consult a medium", "haunted by the ghosts of", "spirits", "victim". These questions can take the following form:

1. What did Sarah's husband left her in his will, and was her emotional state affected by the death of her family?
2. What is a medium? Do you think there is a specific reason why Sarah visited one?
3. What was the medium's advice, and do you think a contemporary medium/psychic would make the same suggestions?

At this stage, the teacher can extend the activity further if the student faces extra difficulty answering the questions in a cohesive manner.

Also, try to personalise the task by asking if a distant relative of theirs, like an aunt or grandma, has inherited such fortune, under

which circumstances, and if those relatives experienced similar fear of spirits. As the student is narrating their personal account of events, remind them to use the vocabulary that they have just been introduced to or other similar vocabulary.

An alternative way to do this is to ask them to reproduce a scene/dialogue, where they reenact the supposed meeting with their aunt and listen as she narrates her story, or to ask them to write the actual dialogue between their aunt and the medium.

If you are dealing with a larger group of students, you can ask them to create the dialogue in pairs and act it out aloud interchangeably, or pass their paper with the dialogue they have just written to a couple of students sitting next to them, to correct any possible errors and add ideas that ameliorate the produced text.

All of the above alternate ways to deal with the same activity can spark the interest of the students to participate in a productive manner.

Thus, as you proceed with the actual reading comprehension activity, it is much more likely that your students will participate more eagerly, and they will use the speaking skills required by the guidelines of the unit.

Usually, the coursebook consists of vocabulary and grammar pages and listening activities in a particular layout (after the brainstorming and the reading comprehension activity). Still, it would be beneficial if you chose not to stick exclusively to the construction of the textbook, even shift the focus when necessary and applicable, to better attend to the needs of the students that require additional help in their speaking skills. This would mean that you could move straight to the speaking activity, leaving the

grammar, vocabulary, and listening pages for later on.

According to the book's speaking task, the student is asked to compare and choose between five ways to uncover the truth that lies beneath local mysteries. At this stage, the book indeed offers some interesting ideas, like borrowing books from a library or doing research on the internet. In this case, the teacher can take on that task and see how the student gradually develops their strategy further down the line.

One more important key factor in knowing how to improve communicative competence is control posture and breathing. Once you have visualized your outcome and have an idea of what the perfect scenario is going to be, begin to include physical preparation as well. Generally neglected, posture has an enormous effect on overall performance. By simply standing up straight, pulling the shoulders back, and looking straight ahead we can deeply affect both physical and mental acuity.

During any presentation, remember the importance of posture, and observe how it affects your breathing. When you stand up straight, you improve the function of your diaphragm, which in turn allows your lungs to process more oxygen. This leads to an overall improvement in heart function and blood flow that ultimately allows your brain to function better, as it gets more blood and oxygen.

As you have now seen, we have many means of improving our capabilities when it comes to communication skills, and or the ability to speak or write effectively. These are things one can practice on a daily basis, and I certainly hope you will do just that. Success is the byproduct of habit, and

good habits are only formed through daily repetition.

You can constantly do things like focus on your posture and make efforts to improve your overall lifestyle in such a way that will optimize performance.

For teachers involved in the learning and preparatory process with students of upper-intermediate level, aiming at a B2 degree, the challenge of overcoming persistent speaking difficulties can be viewed as quite a common occurrence.

It would be counter-productive to have high demands and expectations placed on students who have reached the first and second class of Junior High school, and presume that they will be adequately

equipped to fully respond to complex speaking topics required for the B2 exams, which the majority of coursebooks include in their corpus. Such topics might include unemployment, substance abuse, environmental pollution, societal structures, and others.

Teacher must ask his students' opinion of the coursebook's speaking material, and do not impose the viewpoint of the author. Slowly and steadily, with patience and persistence, make an effort to get them involved in the ideas and arguments they have to develop orally in the speaking questions of each topic in each unit of the coursebook. It is of major significance.

References:

1. Byram, M., Morgan, C., and colleagues. (1994): Teaching-and-Learning- Language-and-Culture. Clevedon: Multilingual Matters.
2. Bachman, L. F., and Palmer, A. S. (1996): Language Testing in Practice. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
3. Littlewood, W. T. 2002. Communicative Language Teaching. : an Introduction. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press
4. Hymes, D. (1972). "On communicative competence". In Pride, J.B., & Holmes, J. (eds.)
5. Hadfield, J. 2005. Elementary Communication Games. Edinburgh: Thomas Nelson and Sons Ltd.
5. www.ziyonet.uz